

5. Metadata harvesting

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📌 Introduction

In this section we describe the harvesting process of the onboarding of metadata to the National Health Data Catalogue. To reach this step your metadata should be mapped to the Health-RI metadata schema. [4A Metadata mapping](#) and FDP should be implemented with metadata exposed: [4B Exposing metadata](#).

✅ Validate metadata

The metadata needs to conform to Health-RI specification. You can use the validator to validate the metadata in your FDP.

1. The metadata can be validated with [Health-RI RDF Validator](#) (see screenshot below)

⚠️ The metadata validator does not traverse through the pages within the FDP. Each page should be validated separately. If multiple datasets, catalogs etc. are present, validate at least one full pathway (ie. Catalog>Dataset>Distribution).

- For *Content to validate*, select “URI”. At *URI*, enter the URI provided by the data holder.
- Content syntax: leave default
- Validate As: select the metadata version you would like to validate against.

2. Make sure there’s “0 errors”

3. If metadata does not pass validation, this **must** be fixed first by the data holder unless given dispensation by both data holder **and** Health-RI team. If you have issues, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

The screenshot shows the 'Health-RI RDF Validator' interface. At the top, it explains that the service validates RDF content against SHACL shapes conforming to Health-RI core metadata shapes. Below this is a form with three main sections: 'Content to validate' (URI dropdown, text input with 'https://fdp.healthdata.nl'), 'Validate as' (dropdown menu with 'v1.0.0 Health-RI core plateau 1' selected and a red annotation 'Select the latest plateau'), and 'Content syntax' (dropdown menu with 'Based on the file extension or response type'). A blue 'Validate' button is below the form. The 'Validation result' section shows an 'Overview' table with the following data: Date: 2024-08-01T08:53:04.672Z, File name: https://fdp.healthdata.nl, Validation type: v1.0.0 Health-RI core plateau 1, Findings: 0 error(s), 0 warning(s), 0 message(s), and Result: SUCCESS (highlighted in green with a red annotation 'Make sure there's no errors'). At the bottom, there are three buttons: 'Download report', 'Download SHACL shapes', and 'Download validated content'.

Contact Health-RI service desk

To harvest the exposed metadata the data holder/provider contacts the Health-RI service desk with an onboarding request and includes the details of the FAIR Data Point to harvest by sending an email to servicedesk@health-ri.nl.

Health-RI then performs the harvesting.

Check the harvested metadata

The metadata is harvested into a testing environment where a check of the data is performed by HRI and the data holder/provider, before reaching the Catalogue. You will receive an email requesting a check of the harvested metadata in the testing environment. If we encountered any issues during the harvesting, we will also notify you. If issues have been identified by the data holder or Health-RI they should be fixed and the process repeated. The Catalogue is currently updated daily for changes in the available FDPs, so changes in the metadata can take up to 24 hours to update.

Metadata is onboarded

If no issues are detected during the harvesting and the harvesting to production environment is approved by the data holder, the data is then onboarding the National Health Data Catalogue. Data can be added to the production environment after 72 hours in the acceptance environment if approved by the data holder.

Questions?

If you have questions about the onboarding process or would like to learn more. Reach out to our [Health-RI Servicedesk](#) | [Health-RI](#)

 servicedesk@health-ri.nl